

HUMAN RESOURCES AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

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Abstract

Human Resources (HR) is one of the most important factors that cannot even be separated from an organization, be it a company or an institution. Business in society scholars have developed many theoretical frameworks intended to map and measure business organisations' roles and impacts in civil society. This is a concern about the relationship between human resources and Corporate Social Responsibility. Quality CSR programs are considered capable of increasing domestic economic development the method used is a qualitative method through a descriptive study. Human resources are the most important asset as the subject of implementing company policies and operational activities. Resources owned by the company such as machines provide optimum results.

Keywords: Bussines, Corporate Social Responsibility, Human Resourches.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are a growing number of studies investigating the responsibility for the realization of social welfare. It is widely accepted that obligation of the government but also involves the participation of other parties. One example is companies and industrial sectors that play an important role in encouraging healthy economic growth (1), (2) showed that business in society scholars have developed many theoretical frameworks intended to map and measure business organisations' roles and impacts in civil society. However, there is practical gap in terms of how seminal social responsibilities of the businessman, management practitioners in general still prefer the narrower economic orientation of the Chicago School to a broader acceptance of social responsibilities.

Good management of CSR is related to the success of the company in integrating CSR policies within the organization. Therefore, CSR should be used as an important need internalized in management systems and business practices and organizational culture (3). Internalization of CSR values is not an easy job, as stated by Dunphy & Benn (4) stating that the development and implementation of CSR strategies are related to considerable changes in the organization. Companies should be able to show that CSR programs are not only realized in physical form in relation to development. The development of human resources (HR) should also receive special attention from the company for the progress of the nation. In order to improve CSR programs that do not forget the importance of human quality development. Quality CSR programs are considered capable of increasing domestic economic development. This paper tries to see the relationship between human resources and corporate social responsibility.

Human Resources (HR) is one of the most important factors that cannot even be separated from an organization, be it a company or an institution. In addition, HR is also a factor that influences the development of a company. In essence, human resources are humans who are employed in an organization who will later become the driving force to be able to achieve the goals of the organization itself. Understanding Human Resources (HR) is generally divided into two, namely human resources at the macro level and human resources at the micro level. Macro human resources are the number of people of productive age in a country. Micro human resources are smaller in scope, namely in individuals who work in an institution. The responsibility of human resources is particularly delegated to the management of human resources (5)

CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) is a social responsibility activity from a company to the community and the environment for the impact of its business activities. CSR itself stands for Corporate Social Responsibility, or Corporate Social Responsibility. Basically, CSR is the company's responsibility to the stakeholders, and also the company's responsibility to the shareholders. Actually, until now the definition of CSR is still diverse and has different definitions from one another. (6) Corporate Social Responsibility is an activity carried out by each company as a sense of corporate responsibility towards the community around the environment where a company carries out its activities. Thus the company must have an awareness of how influential and important the welfare of the community around the company. Many ways can be done by the company in carrying out its role for the welfare of the surrounding community, for example providing funds for public facilities, giving scholarships or making donations to build villages and so on. CSR' expresses more than simply the requirement that business should be conducted ethically – it refers to the notion of responsibility

2. METHODOLOGY

The method used is a qualitative method through a descriptive study. Data collection techniques in this research proposal, namely: by observation or direct observation by looking at the interactions carried out by the institution in the use of Administrative Sciences. Literature Study, where researchers examine books, scientific articles, online media, and other print media. Determine research informants, such as leaders and staff who have used Capita Selekt in Administrative Sciences.

The implementation time of this research is 8 months from the preparation stage to the reporting stage. The results of this study are the role of HR and human resource management is fairly important, namely determining the factors of production, building, and developing the company. If there are no qualified and adequate human resources, the company will automatically fail to achieve the goals it wants to achieve.

3. RESULTS

The results of direct observations or observations obtained in the field. The discussion in this study was obtained from the results that all employees totaling 160 employees with dominant male sex, aged between 26-40 years old, Muslim, with 1-5 years of service. Caused by several things which can be explained as follows: Workforce diversity means that the organization increasingly heterogeneous in terms of gender, age, ethnicity, race and religion. A number of the literature has explained that diversity when treated positive, can increase creativity and innovation in the organization, at the same time improve decision making by providing different perspectives on various issues. However, when differences are not treated properly there is a potential for higher employee turnover, more difficult communication and more interpersonal conflict.

Further research was conducted by Seif Obeid Alshbiel and Waleed M. AL-Awawdeh in Jordan. The research entitled "Internal Social Responsibility and its Impact on Job Commitment: Empirical Study of Jordanian Cement Manufacturing Co", the results of the study statistically showed that there was a strong and significant relationship. According to the study, the other side of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) related to employees is usually related to an activity that is directly connected physically and psychologically, because employees find themselves in the organization. Moreover, if social activities and practices (CSR) are adopted by top management, it will foster a work climate that supports relationships between people in the workplace. Human resources are the most important assets as the subject of implementing policies and company operational activities. The resources owned by the company such as capital, methods and machines cannot provide optimum results if they are not supported by human resources. Human resource development, Human Resources Development or HRD is increasingly being seen as having a role in helping organizations achieve their social, environmental and economic goals. The contribution of HRD in a societal context can be understood through a company's resource-based view (RBV), because company resources represent not only assets but also create value. Therefore, when organizations pursue socially focused initiatives, these can be a source of competitive advantage and enable the company to operate in a sustainable and ethical manne.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Human Resources and human resource management are fairly important, namely determining factors of production, building, and developing companies. If there are no qualified and adequate human resources, the company will automatically fail to achieve the goals it wants to achieve. In addition, the existence of HR is also a key factor in determining the success and success of a company or organization.

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